

Chemical Behaviour of Humic Substances at High pH

I. Titrations after End Point

M. ADHIKARI and P. SEN

Department of Agriculture, Calcutta University, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta-700 019

Manuscript received 16 March 1983, accepted 26 May 1984

The alkali consumption by natural and synthetic humic substances even after the complete neutralisation of acidic functional groups was investigated. Of the humic substances the excess alkali consumption after the end point was maximum in case of naturally occurring humic substances. The lower the E_4/E_6 values greater is the alkali consumption even after end point of neutralisation in acidity indicating greater aromaticity in the molecule. The presence of organically bound Fe^{++} and Al^{++} in a synthetic humic acid may contribute significantly to the consumption of alkali. The excess alkali required to stabilise the pH at 8.0 in case of synthetic humic acid prepared from glucose is due to the conversion of sugars to enols and then to its isomeric forms.

OXIDATION of humic substances under alkaline condition is an well known fact but so far little has been known about the chemical reactions in absence of oxygen¹. It was reported² that excess alkali was consumed even after the complete neutralisation of the acidic groups by titration under an inert atmosphere. It was suggested that additional acidic groups were exposed due to the change in pH specially in the pH range 7.0-8.0. Humic acid with NaOH (*N*) was treated under nitrogen and oxygen atmosphere³. Treatment with alkali under N_2 produces some changes of humic substances like the reduction in molecular weight, small reduction in uv and visible O.D. and hydrolytic release of amino-acids. The difference in structural orientations of humic/fulvic acid with change in pH was observed by scanning electron microscopy⁴. The humic materials changed from fibres and bundles of fibres at low pH, to a finely woven net work at intermediate pH, and plastic type sheets and fine grains at high pH.

In light of the above facts, attempts have been made to compare the conformational changes on the polyelectrolyte chains of different humic substances with the addition of alkali.

Experimental

Humic acid was extracted from Mohitnagar soil by NaOH solution (0.1*N*) the by usual technique⁵. Humic acid was synthesized in laboratory from a mixture of catechol and glycine using Ca-clay (pH 8.2) and also in a medium containing Fe and Al oxide gels as catalysts. The humic acid synthesized using different catalysts are denoted as follows: Ca-clay (with oxide), Syn HA I; Ca-clay (without oxide), Syn HA II; Fe and Al oxide gels, Syn HA III. The details of the procedure of synthesis of humic substances using clay and non-clay catalyst

and synthesis of humic acid from glucose were reported earlier^{6,7}.

The pH-metric titrations were carried out with the aid of an Elico LI-10 pH meter. The O.D. values of samples at 465 and 665 nm were measured with an Elico CL-24 spectrophotometer. The concentration of each sample was 5 mg ml⁻¹. The humic acids were adjusted at pH 7.0, 8.0 and 10.0 and the fulvic acid at pH 5.0, 7.0, 8.0 and 10.0 with NaOH (E. Merck G. R.) solution (0.01 *N*). The pH values were so chosen because they covered the range at which the dissociation of acidic functional groups occur. Excess alkali was added to maintain high pH values when it fell more than 0.05 units. The experiments were carried out in stoppered glass bottle.

Result and Discussion

It is evident from Table 1 that for the humic acid samples, the time and quantities of alkali required to stabilise pH increases with increasing pH. The total alkali consumption in meq for stabilising pH in case of fulvic acid is more than any of the samples studied. Of the humic acids total alkali consumption is maximum in case of naturally occurring humic substances (Mohitnagar humic acid) than the synthetic humic acids. From the E_4/E_6 values alkali consumption for stabilising pH increases, *i.e.* the alkali consumption increases with the increase in aromatic character of humic acids. Humic acid prepared from glucose consumes considerable amount of alkali which might be due to the fact that sugars are considerably altered even under mild alkaline solutions. This conversion is known as Lobry, de Bruyn-Alberda, van Eckenstein transformation⁸. Alkali has one of the three following actions on sugars⁹, (i) isomerization mainly at the reducing end of the sugars, (ii)

TABLE 1

Polyelectrolyte solution	pH	NaOH added initially meq	Time for stable pH h	Total NaOH consumed meq
Syn HA I	7.0	1.5×10^{-3}	16	2.5×10^{-3}
Syn HA I	8.0	2.0×10^{-3}	37	5.0×10^{-3}
Syn HA I	10.0	4.0×10^{-3}	42	1.2×10^{-1}
Syn HA II	7.0	1.2×10^{-3}	7	2.0×10^{-3}
Syn HA II	8.0	2.5×10^{-3}	22	3.2×10^{-3}
Syn HA II	10.0	3.5×10^{-3}	38	4.8×10^{-3}
Syn HA III	7.0	1.0×10^{-3}	8	2.25×10^{-3}
Syn HA III	8.0	2.6×10^{-3}	28	4.3×10^{-3}
Syn HA III	10.0	4.4×10^{-3}	45	6.8×10^{-3}
Natural HA	7.0	2.0×10^{-1}	18	2.05×10^{-1}
Natural HA	8.0	2.3×10^{-1}	52	2.4×10^{-1}
Natural HA	10.0	2.5×10^{-1}	56	2.7×10^{-1}
HA (glucose)	7.0	1.0×10^{-3}	8	2.0×10^{-3}
HA (glucose)	8.0	1.5×10^{-3}	14	2.5×10^{-3}
HA (glucose)	10.0	1.85×10^{-3}	18	2.65×10^{-3}
FA (natural)	5.0	15.15×10^{-3}	-	1.515×10^{-1}
FA (natural)	7.0	24.0×10^{-3}	14	2.5×10^{-1}
FA (natural)	8.0	25.5×10^{-3}	48	2.65×10^{-1}
FA (natural)	10.0	32.0×10^{-3}	76	3.55×10^{-1}

HA = Humic acid, FA = Fulvic acid.

fragmentation into parts having fewer carbon atoms, and (iii) internal oxidation and reduction. Enolisation is the initial step of all the above transformations.

It is also evident from Table 1 that more alkali is needed in case of synthetic humic acid HA III to attain the pH 10. This might be due to the presence of organically bound Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} which may absorb hydroxyl ions to form Fe- and Al-hydroxides, similar to the results reported^{9,10}. It is stated earlier that alkali consumption and time required for stabilising pH of natural humic substances are more than the synthetic humic acids. This higher amount of alkali consumption is mainly due to the following factors.

(a) Presence of greater molecular complexity in natural humic substances having molecular weight ($M_v=28245$).

(b) Presence of more dissociable acidic functional groups. From Table 2 it is noted that the E_4/E_6 value of natural humic acid is minimum, which indicates the presence of a condensed aromatic structure in it. Furthermore, the ir spectra (not shown) of the natural humic acid showed a strong absorption at 1090 cm^{-1} due to presence of cyclic aliphatic esters and alcohols. The presence

of condensed aromatic network and higher amount of ester groups in the natural humic acid than the synthetic humic acids⁷ may be a reason for excess alkali consumption.

TABLE 2

Sample	E_4/E_6 (pH 8.0)
Natural HA	0.440
Syn HA I	0.854
Syn HA II	1.425
Syn HA III	0.931
HA (glucose)	5.200

Although the E_4/E_6 values of fulvic acid is greater than most of the humic acid samples (except the humic acid from glucose), it consumes significant amount of alkali mainly due to presence of excess acidic functional groups (CEC 856 meq/100 g). Moreover, the presence of carbohydrate molecules, mainly sugars may be a reason for excess alkali consumption because they can consume alkali to undergo chemical alterations. This is further supported from the experimental facts that humic acid prepared from glucose consumes considerable amount of alkali, though it has low molecular weight and simple molecular structure¹¹.

References

1. W. FLAIG, H. BEUTELSPACHER and E. REITZ, in "Chemical Composition and Physical Properties of Humic Substances in Soil Components", ed. J. E. GIESKING, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1975, Vol. 1, pp. 1-24.
2. H. DAVIS and C. J. B. MOTT, *J. Soil. Sci.*, 1981, 32, 393.
3. R. S. SWIFT and A. M. POSNER, *J. Soil. Sci.*, 1972, 23, 381.
4. N. SENSI, Y. CHEN and M. SCHNITZER, "Soil Organic Matter Studies", I.A.E.A., Vienna, 1977, Vol. 2.
5. M. M. KONONOVA, "Soil Organic Matter", Pergamon, Oxford, 1968.
6. M. ADHIKARI, B. MANDAL and T. K. MUKHERJEE, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. A*, 1978, 44, 202.
7. M. ADHIKARI, P. SEN and P. BANDHOPADHYAY, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India*, submitted for publication.
8. P. R. BLOOM, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1979, 43, 815.
9. P. R. BLOOM and M. B. MCBRIDE, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1979, 43, 687.
10. R. U. LEMIEUX, in "Molecular Rearrangements", ed. P. DEMEYO, Interscience, New York, 1964, pp. 733-35.
11. M. ADHIKARI, B. MANDAL and P. SEN, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. A*, 1980, 46, 387.